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**REHABILITATION AS A TOOL FOR MANAGING THE URBAN
ENVIRONMENT**

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Abstract: The article examines the most important aspects and stages of the rehabilitation process in urban environmental management and improving the quality of landscape design. Using a city as an example, it demonstrates the need to develop targeted rehabilitation of the urban environment by improving the urban greening system.

Keywords: urban environment, urban environmental rehabilitation, urban environmental management, landscape design, urban greening system.

The problem of disturbed territories has been around for a long time, but a comprehensive approach to their rehabilitation has only been implemented in recent decades. The expansion of human influence forces us to consider issues related to environmental interventions on a global scale. Never before have there been situations that raised the question of the destruction of all life on Earth. Human activity has reached such a scale that an environmental disaster (along with humanitarian, military, and other disasters) in one region immediately negatively impacts the entire global ecosystem.

Of course, the destruction of land by quarries, especially near large settlements, does not have the same detrimental impact on people's lives as, for example, air pollution from vehicle exhaust or chemical contamination of water bodies. However, quarries have recently become a stumbling block between environmental organizations and the destructive forces of nature—the mining companies.

Numerous lawsuits against quarry managements and orders to cease mining operations near cities all speak to society's desire to address these issues. Environmental problems force humanity to consider its future path of development: should it become a consumer society, living only in the present, or should it take into account the potential

of the natural environment and align its actions with the goals of social development in the near future.

Human activity today is global in nature, so it's necessary to broadly consider the quarry landscape as an integral, important part of the overall environmental crisis. Previously, local human impacts on the Earth's surface were quite significant, lasted for a long time, and allowed nature to recover. In other words, "the biosphere's adaptive self-regulation mechanisms were able to operate, and it remained an integrated system capable of supporting life."

Creating a favorable habitat for all types of human activity is linked to the rehabilitation of various types of urban spaces and presupposes providing city residents not only with convenient and comfortable housing, but also with a high level of socialization of the city's spatial environment, i.e., saturating urban spaces with elements of improvement, landscaping, maintenance, and design.

Creative areas such as architectural design, including urban and landscape design, are currently gaining increasing importance in urban rehabilitation. These types of urban planning are popular today precisely because of the need to provide urban rehabilitation programs with highly qualified specialists, which is an important strategic step for future work on the urban environment.

Urban rehabilitation involves multi-year programs to improve the quality of urban space, "humanizing" it, and "individualizing" it through aesthetic means. Depending on the quality of our surroundings, including the architectural and landscape organization of small urban spaces (courtyards, public gardens, pedestrian and public areas, etc.), the urban environment can have both beneficial and detrimental effects on human health. The placement and design of small architectural forms, such as public transportation stops, gas stations, mini-markets, outdoor advertising, street furniture, landscaping and improvements, etc., also play a significant role in the quality of the urban environment.

Therefore, when designing silhouette urban ensembles, we must not forget about the design of the urban environment as a form of aesthetic impact on people. The placement of individual elements and complexes of small architectural forms, advertising, sculpture, and the careful selection of greenery varieties based on their aesthetic properties, typically perceived by the human eye, will influence the subconscious of citizens, cultivating their taste and culture. To effectively manage the development of existing urban spaces, many cities have now begun developing programs for targeted urban rehabilitation.

The goal of any rehabilitation is to improve the quality of the urban environment and, consequently, enhance the standard of living of city residents. The essence of this action lies in the most effective use of the territory's potential, namely, ensuring sustainable development, increasing its competitiveness, enhancing its aesthetic qualities, and developing its socio-economic potential.

"Urban environment" and "environment" in general are used in various meanings. From a human perspective, the urban environment is the totality of living conditions for the population. The urban environment is a fundamental concept expressing the deep essence of the city both as a place where large numbers of people congregate and as a functional entity that plays such a crucial role in the life and development of society and its territorial organization. Furthermore, the urban environment is an important component of the city's potential, thanks to which it fulfills its historical mission as an engine of progress. A diverse and multi-faceted urban environment fosters the emergence and development of new content in various spheres of human activity.

Urban space significantly influences not only the daily behavior and worldview of city residents, but also the long-term and fundamental processes of civil society development: trust in public institutions, relationships between social groups, norms and stereotypes of behavior, attitudes toward historical heritage, and the conditions for the formation of youth worldviews.

A city's greening system, as an integral part of urban open spaces, is of great importance for improving the quality of the urban environment, as well as for the architectural and planning organization of the city. The concept of a city-wide greening system encompasses the entire set of urban green structures: their placement within the city, their interconnections with each other, and with green spaces in the suburban area. Green spaces create a healthy environment for work, life, and recreation for the population. Moreover, their effectiveness depends both on their quantity and on the extent to which they form a coherent, continuous system that permeates all parts of the city.

A city's greening system can be divided into three groups of green spaces. The first group includes green spaces for public use (city and district parks, gardens in residential areas and microdistricts, squares and boulevards), while the second group includes green spaces for limited use (landscapes in residential areas and childcare facilities, gardens at public buildings, hospitals, etc.). The third group includes green spaces for special purposes (botanical and zoological gardens, sanitary protection zones, nurseries, water protection zones, etc.).

Fig. 1. Some theoretical schemes reflecting historical concepts of open urban space and its relationship with the natural environment:

1 – J. Perret's ideal city. A ring of open spaces around the fortress walls; within the city, open spaces are virtually absent;

2 – The city from Morelli's "Code of Nature" – the idea of breaking up urban development with open spaces;

3 – The creation of a belt of public parks and a belt of gardens and farms around the compact city. The "model" plan of the colonial city by G. Sharp (1794);

4 – The ring-shaped concentric structure with alternating built-up and open spaces in the city by C. Fourier (1820);

5 – The suburban area of Thunen. The city is surrounded by a belt of intensive agriculture, a belt of forests, and a belt of extensive agriculture (1826);

6 – The first "water-green diameter" in the utopian plan of E. Cabet (1840).

Before the emergence of large industrial cities in the 19th century, the city was viewed as a stable entity, isolated from its surroundings. Ideal theoretical schemes were

interpreted in elementary geometric forms, dominated by ring-shaped and concentric structures (the schemes of J. Perret, G. Sharp, C. Fourier, and others, (Fig. 1.)).

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In global urban planning practice, a number of theoretical schemes for urban greening systems have emerged in design proposals for cities of the future. Most theoretical proposals for urban planning structures outline systems with central and peripheral placement of city green zones, the organization of green "rings," "spots," and "wedges." Linear-strip and combined schemes. All of these systems share two key criteria: uniform distribution of park green spaces and their easy accessibility from residential areas by transport and pedestrians. Combined green space systems, based on a combination of elements from centric, peripheral, group, and linear-strip greening systems, have also become widespread in urban planning.

One of the conditions for developing a comprehensive greening system is ensuring the continuity of green spaces. This creates comfortable conditions for pedestrian traffic and the placement of sports facilities. The unifying elements of the city's greening system are boulevards, pedestrian streets, and pedestrian alleys. They are designed to direct the flow of pedestrian traffic to public transportation stops, work areas, and service facilities.

The functional planning structure and ecology of a city are primarily influenced by public green spaces, as they occupy a significant portion of its territory, including large natural landscape areas along riverbanks and suburban areas.

Therefore, one of the most important conditions for the rehabilitation of the urban environment is the formation of spatial systems that include types of green spaces and natural landscape areas of varying sizes and functional purposes. These should include small residential courtyards and public squares; urban gardens and parks; large natural landscape areas of river floodplains; and suburban recreation areas. To create a

continuous green system, all green spaces should be connected by alleys, boulevards, and pedestrian streets.

Such a green system will encourage residents to move around without the use of transport, create conditions for physical fitness and recreation in the suburban environment, and contribute to the restoration of the ecological balance of the urban environment, which will have a beneficial effect on the physical and spiritual health of city residents.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Grimanova, I. General Plan for an Old Quarry. "Architecture," Supplement to Stroitel'naya Gazeta, No. 6, 1984.

2. Vikhansky, O.S. Strategic Management: A Textbook / O.S. Vikhansky. Moscow: Gardarika, 1998.

3. [ПРОБЛЕМЫ ШИРОКОГО ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ «ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ПРИНЦИПОВ» В ЖИЛИЩНОМ СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ](#)

4. ШГ Муминов, ГА Сереева - ... и архитектурная среда: вопросы исторического и ..., 2021

5. Demidova, E.V. Rehabilitation of Urban Spaces: Experience, Retrospective, and Problems of Uralniiproekt RAASN – "Project Akhay." Yekaterinburg, 2010.

6. Zub, A.T. Strategic Management: Theory and Practice / A.T. Zub. Moscow: Aspekt PRESS, 2002.